

1 Percentile-Level Examination of Ten Acoustic Indicators

2 **Pinpoints Urban Noise Factors Affecting Noise Effects on Pedestrians**

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12 **ABSTRACT**

13 This study examines how different temporal acoustic percentiles can enhance the analysis
14 of urban noise effects on pedestrians. Traditional noise indicators, typically focusing on
15 energy averages, are expanded by considering statistical temporal structures to better
16 correlate with subjective noise effects. Data was gathered via simultaneous noise
17 measurements and pedestrian surveys across streets with different traffic conditions.
18 Noise indicators, including L_{AF} , L_{Aeq} , L_{Zeq} , L_{Cpeak} , L_{AFmax} , etc., were analysed at multiple
19 percentiles (L_1 , L_5 , L_{10} , L_{50} , L_{90} , L_{95} , L_{99}).

20 Results indicated that temporal percentiles substantially improved the predictive power
21 for various noise effects. Among all percentiles analysed, L_{50} emerged as universally
22 effective, closely correlating with subjective measures such as irritability, conversation
23 interruption, and overall noise perception. Specific effects, such as startle and auditory

24 annoyance, correlated more strongly with background noise levels (L_{AF90} , L_{AF95} , L_{AF99}).
25 Additionally, high-level noise indicators (L_{Cpeak} and L_{AFmax}) showed improved correlation
26 with noise effects when considered through percentiles rather than conventional values.
27 The study suggests that temporal statistical analysis offers critical insight beyond
28 traditional energy-based noise measures. It further highlights the significance of
29 frequency weighting in noise assessment, advocating the use of Z or C weightings rather
30 than the common A weighting, especially for predicting irritability or startle. Ultimately,
31 incorporating temporal acoustic percentiles can substantially enhance the accuracy of
32 predicting how urban noise affects people's daily experiences.

33

34 **Keywords:** effects of noise, noise perception, noise annoyance, irritability, startle,
35 disturbance in spoken communication, environmental noise.

36

37 **1. Introduction**

38 Environmental noise is considered a major pollutant due to its negative impact, especially
39 on the population in urban environments (Fu et al., 2022) (Hahad et al., 2022) (Jimenez
40 et al., 2023) (Starke et al., 2023) and on both wildlife and territory in natural areas
41 (Shannon et al., 2016) (Kight and Swaddle, 2011) (Sánchez-Fernández et al., 2022)
42 (Bruschi et al., 2015). The fight against noise pollution is a major challenge for
43 contemporary society due to various noise sources, such as transportation, industrial
44 areas, construction, and leisure activities (Garg, 2022) (Montes González et al., 2024)
45 (Silva et al., 2021) (Ballesteros et al., 2014) and whose predominance depends on the type
46 of environment evaluated. Public administrations face complexity in decision-making
47 when adopting action plans for noise abatement, since it is necessary to harmonize the

48 different interests and uses of public space that may exist. In addition, it is essential to
49 take into consideration the characteristics and conditions of the environment in which the
50 noise mitigation measures would be implemented (Licitra et al., 2017) (Paschalidou et
51 al., 2019), as well as the different factors on which each noise source depends (Thompson,
52 2024) (Zhao et al., 2020) (Sánchez-Fernández et al., 2021).

53 The assessment of environmental noise exposure in the area where the action plans need
54 to be implemented seems to be the first logical step to take to determine the baseline
55 acoustic situation. In this regard, in situ measurements are a methodology that provides
56 fairly accurate and reliable results of the existing noise levels (Zagubień and Wolniewicz,
57 2024) (Vílchez-Gómez et al., 2023) (Quintero et al., 2021). However, if the area under
58 evaluation is large, such as an entire city, the costs associated with this methodology may
59 be a factor to be considered. It is common in this type of scenarios to use methodologies
60 that combine both measurements and acoustic simulations by means of computational
61 models, which with proper planning allow obtaining results of noise levels with a limited
62 uncertainty (Law et al., 2011) (Licitra and Memoli, 2008) (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2021).
63 However, studies based only on acoustic measurements have an important advantage over
64 simulations, such as the possibility of obtaining different types of more specific acoustic
65 variables such as indicators related to the maximum and minimum sound energy (L_{max} ,
66 L_{min}), temporal noise indicators (L_N), indicators related to the frequency spectrum (L_{Zeq} ,
67 L_{Aeq} , L_{Ceq} , $L_{eq20-200Hz}$, SIL , $PSIL$) (Maristany et al., 2016) (Swain et al., 2023) (Barrigón
68 Morillas et al., 2024a).

69 If a study of this type is to be carried out in an urban environment, it should be taken into
70 account in the design of the working methodology that, although there is a diversity of
71 noise sources, road traffic is the one to which a higher percentage of the population is
72 usually exposed (EEA, 2020) (Rey-Gozalo et al., 2022). Measurements to conduct a fully

73 experimental study or to validate the computational calculation model should be carried
74 out using a sampling method representative of the spatial and temporal variability of the
75 sound source (Quintero et al., 2019) (Brambilla et al., 2023) (Barrigón Morillas et al.,
76 2024b). The multiple factors on which road traffic noise depends, such as vehicle flow,
77 speed, type of pavement, urban and architectural characteristics of the city and
78 environmental conditions, should also be considered in the planning of the study
79 (Guarnaccia et al., 2024) (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2022) (Ascari et al., 2023) (Sanchez
80 et al., 2016) (Barros et al., 2023) (Deng et al., 2025). In addition to the aforementioned
81 aspects, it is also important in the planning of the study to select the acoustic indicators
82 that need to be considered according to the objectives to be achieved. In this sense, sound
83 variables that allow considering the temporal, frequency and energy aspects of urban
84 noise can be useful. Some indicators commonly used in the scientific literature in acoustic
85 studies in cities are L_{eq} , L_{min} , L_{max} , L_N and L_{peak} , to some of which frequency (A, C) and
86 time (S, F, I) weightings are applied (Tao et al., 2020) (Song et al., 2024) (Barrigon
87 Morillas et al., 2024a) (Paszkowski et al., 2018). Kasess et al. use certain percentiles (the
88 median and the value that was exceeded 5 % of the time) of some acoustical and
89 psychoacoustical indicators to explain the annoyance produced by noise generated by
90 heat pumps (Kasess et al., 2020). Chang et al. (2024), analysing the relationship between
91 acoustic indicators and the perception of noisiness in a hospital environment, found that
92 the L_{10} percentile of L_{Aeq} was the best predictor of perceived noisiness in waiting areas
93 used by staff in a children's hospital. Additionally, Fiebig and Sottek (2015) investigated
94 the relationship between perceived loudness and certain temporal characteristics of
95 sound. In their study, both peak and background loudness levels were found to
96 significantly contribute to overall loudness assessments. These studies highlight the need
97 to further explore the relationship between noise effects and the temporal characteristics

98 of the sound environment. Öhrström et al. (2006) used the $L_{Aeq,24h}$ indicator to examine
99 the relationship between road traffic noise and general annoyance, indoor daytime
100 activities (such as communication, relaxation, concentration, and listening to radio or
101 television), and several health and well-being variables (e.g., feeling irritated or angry,
102 worried, and nervous).

103 In addition to conducting a study of urban noise by means of objective indicators, for
104 making decisions regarding noise mitigation plans it is also useful to assess the perception
105 of the effects of noise pollution by the inhabitants of the city (Li et al., 2025) (Lin et al.,
106 2025) (Barros et al., 2024) (Moriyama et al., 2022). This allows understanding of the
107 subjective perceptions of residents regarding noise impacts on their quality of life,
108 assessing aspects such as annoyance, satisfaction with the sound environment and the
109 possible disturbances of this pollutant agent in their everyday activities (Pasanen et al.,
110 2025) (Köklü et al., 2025) (Li et al., 2022) (Myllyntausta et al., 2020). Although there are
111 different survey methodologies, conducting on-site surveys to pedestrians together with
112 the acoustic measurements in that street can be a very interesting technique, as the noise
113 indicators closely reflect the acoustic conditions in the time frame in which people answer
114 the questions.

115 This paper presents experimental research involving simultaneous on-site surveys and
116 noise measurements to study the relationships between some subjective variables
117 associated with effects of urban noise in pedestrians and some objective indicators related
118 to the temporal characteristics of sound environment. The primary scientific novelty of
119 this study is the introduction of a new approach using percentile levels of some traditional
120 sound indicators to study the relationship with noise effects. In Section 2, the
121 methodology used for simultaneous acoustic measurements and pedestrian surveys in
122 diverse urban environments is detailed. Section 3 presents and discusses the significant

123 findings related to the correlations between subjective noise effects and various acoustic
124 temporal percentiles, highlighting the effectiveness of non-standard acoustic indicators.
125 Finally, Section 4 summarizes the key conclusions derived from the analysis,
126 emphasizing the relevance of temporal noise characteristics and their implications for
127 predicting noise effects in urban settings.

128

129 **2. Method**

130 A study was conducted based on simultaneous in situ surveys and noise measurements in
131 the streets of Cáceres (Spain). A previous categorization of urban streets based on their
132 traffic circulation functionality (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2021) was used as a reference to
133 design the sampling method, ensuring variability in urban characteristics and traffic
134 flows. Objective and subjective variables were collected through measurements and
135 surveys at 29 randomly selected sampling points (Fig. 1) on urban streets classified into
136 different categories during daytime working hours. A random sample stratified by age
137 group and gender was taken with the aim of obtaining a sample with an age structure and
138 gender ratio similar to that of the city being evaluated (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2024a).

139

140

141 Figure 1. Sampling points in Cáceres (from Google Earth)

142

143 In situ noise measurements of 15-minute duration were conducted simultaneously with
144 the surveys, ensuring sufficient spatial separation between measurement and survey
145 points to prevent interference with recorded noise levels. A class 1 sound level meter-
146 analyser was utilized to measure objective acoustic variables, alongside a class 1 sound
147 calibrator for verifying calibration accuracy before and after each measurement series.
148 Noise measurements adhered to the general guidelines provided by the ISO 1996-2
149 standard (*ISO 1996-2*, 2017) and methodologies described in recent literature (Zagubień
150 and Wolniewicz, 2021) (Montes González et al., 2020) (Mateus et al., 2015). The
151 microphone was positioned 1.5 m above ground level, 2 m from the nearest reflective

152 façades, and similarly distanced from the closest point of the primary noise source (road
153 traffic).

154 The survey comprised nine questions, each rated on an 11-point numerical scale ranging
155 from 0 (nothing or never) to 10 (totally or always), addressing the effects of urban noise
156 on pedestrians. The survey comprised nine questions, each rated on an 11-point numerical
157 scale ranging from 0 (nothing or never) to 10 (totally or always), addressing the effects
158 of urban noise on pedestrians. More detailed information on the survey is included in
159 Supplementary Material. In cases where signs of hearing impairment were identified
160 during the interview, the respondent's data was excluded from the analysis. This survey
161 has been designed, pretested, and validated in previous studies (Rey Gozalo et al., 2017,
162 2018). The internal consistency of the items in this study shows a high Cronbach's alpha
163 (0.93). In addition, in the validation of the construct through factor analysis, a KMO of
164 0.97 and a principal component encompassing the different items with a percentage of
165 explained variance greater than 65% were obtained.

166 The subjective variables obtained from surveys and the objective variables recorded from
167 acoustic measurements are listed respectively in Table 1 and Table 2. Regarding
168 subjective variables, respondents were first asked to indicate the extent or frequency with
169 which environmental noise on the street caused them: a) irritability; b) startle; c)
170 annoyance in the ears; d) interrupting a conversation with someone nearby; e) raising the
171 volume of their voice to speak with someone nearby; f) interrupting a phone conversation;
172 and g) raising the volume of their voice on a phone conversation. Participants
173 subsequently rated (h) acoustic perception of the environment on that street, and (i) the
174 degree to which the noise annoyed them during the survey. The simultaneous timing of
175 the sound measurements and surveys, together with the interviewers' experience, were
176 decisive in controlling for confounding factors.

177

178 Table 1. Subjective variables registered in during the survey.

Subjective variables	Meaning
a)	Irritability
b)	Startle
c)	Annoyance ears
d)	Interrupting conversation
e)	Raising volume
f)	Interrupting phone
g)	Raising phone
h)	Noisy street
i)	Annoyance

179

180 Table 2. Objective variables registered during the measurements and their percentiles

Objective variables	Percentiles of objective variables						
<i>L_{AF}</i>	<i>L_{AF1}</i>	<i>L_{AF5}</i>	<i>L_{AF10}</i>	<i>L_{AF50}</i>	<i>L_{AF90}</i>	<i>L_{AF95}</i>	<i>L_{AF99}</i>
<i>L_{Zeq}</i>	<i>L_{Zeq1}</i>	<i>L_{Zeq5}</i>	<i>L_{Zeq10}</i>	<i>L_{Zeq50}</i>	<i>L_{Zeq90}</i>	<i>L_{Zeq95}</i>	<i>L_{Zeq99}</i>
<i>L_{Aeq}</i>	<i>L_{Aeq1}</i>	<i>L_{Aeq5}</i>	<i>L_{Aeq10}</i>	<i>L_{Aeq50}</i>	<i>L_{Aeq90}</i>	<i>L_{Aeq95}</i>	<i>L_{Aeq99}</i>
<i>L_{Ceq}</i>	<i>L_{Ceq1}</i>	<i>L_{Ceq5}</i>	<i>L_{Ceq10}</i>	<i>L_{Ceq50}</i>	<i>L_{Ceq90}</i>	<i>L_{Ceq95}</i>	<i>L_{Ceq99}</i>
<i>L_{A1eq}</i>	<i>L_{A1eq1}</i>	<i>L_{A1eq5}</i>	<i>L_{A1eq10}</i>	<i>L_{A1eq50}</i>	<i>L_{A1eq90}</i>	<i>L_{A1eq95}</i>	<i>L_{A1eq99}</i>
Loudness	<i>Loudness₁</i>	<i>Loudness₅</i>	<i>Loudness₁₀</i>	<i>Loudness₅₀</i>	<i>Loudness₉₀</i>	<i>Loudness₉₅</i>	<i>Loudness₉₉</i>
Loudness level	<i>level₁</i>	<i>level₅</i>	<i>level₁₀</i>	<i>level₅₀</i>	<i>level₉₀</i>	<i>level₉₅</i>	<i>level₉₉</i>
<i>L_{Cpeak}</i>	<i>L_{Cpeak1}</i>	<i>L_{Cpeak5}</i>	<i>L_{Cpeak10}</i>	<i>L_{Cpeak50}</i>	<i>L_{Cpeak90}</i>	<i>L_{Cpeak95}</i>	<i>L_{Cpeak99}</i>
<i>L_{AFmax}</i>	<i>L_{AFmax1}</i>	<i>L_{AFmax5}</i>	<i>L_{AFmax10}</i>	<i>L_{AFmax50}</i>	<i>L_{AFmax90}</i>	<i>L_{AFmax95}</i>	<i>L_{AFmax99}</i>
<i>L_{AFmin}</i>	<i>L_{AFmin1}</i>	<i>L_{AFmin5}</i>	<i>L_{AFmin10}</i>	<i>L_{AFmin50}</i>	<i>L_{AFmin90}</i>	<i>L_{AFmin95}</i>	<i>L_{AFmin99}</i>

181

182 An analysis was conducted to investigate the relationships between subjective variables
 183 related to the perceived effects of noise on pedestrians (Table 1) and acoustic variables
 184 reflecting the statistical temporal characteristics of urban noise environments (Table 2).

185 For this study, acoustic variables were divided into two groups. The first group included
 186 standard acoustic variables, encompassing the percentiles traditionally employed in
 187 environmental acoustics derived from instantaneous sound pressure levels with A and F
 188 frequency weightings. The second group comprised what were called non-standard
 189 acoustic variables. These were calculated as typical percentiles (*L₁*, *L₅*, *L₁₀*, *L₅₀*, *L₉₀*, *L₉₅*,

190 and L_{99}) but based on second-by-second records of traditional acoustic indicators that
191 generally do not have percentiles computed: L_{Zeq} , L_{Ceq} , L_{Aeq} , L_{A1eq} , Loudness, Loudness
192 Level, L_{Cpeak} , L_{AFmax} , and L_{AFmin} .

193 The percentiles used have been selected to characterise in urban environments: the
194 background noise level, or levels that are exceeded between 90 % and 99 % of the
195 assessment time (L_{90} , L_{95} , L_{99}); a mean value indicator (L_{50}), 50 % of the time the
196 indicator is above - or below - this value; and the highest noise levels, or levels that are
197 exceeded between 1 % and 10 % of the time (L_1 , L_5 , L_{10}). To calculate the time percentiles
198 of the noise indicators, after recording their values in every second of the 15-minute
199 measurement period, the noise level that is exceeded during the corresponding percentage
200 of the time (1%, 5%, 10%, 50%, 90%, 95% and 99%) is determined. The acoustic
201 indicators consider: 1) different spectral weightings in order to adapt the measured sound
202 level to the frequency response of the human ear as a function of the sound level (Z, C, A
203 or variable with the level); 2) incorporating different time weightings, either with a
204 historical origin related to the first analogue sound level meters (S and F), defined to
205 simulate the response of the ear to impulsive noises (I) or to measure this type of noise
206 from the maximum sound pressure reached during the measurement period (peak); 3)
207 taking into account the masking effect of some sounds on others (Loudness, Loudness
208 Level). Finally, these aspects are considered in the followings indicators with different
209 frequency and time weightings o with masking effects: 1) to evaluate the average sound
210 energy during the evaluation period without masking effect (L_{Zeq} , L_{Ceq} , L_{Aeq} and L_{A1eq}) o
211 with masking effects (Loudness and Loudness Level) and 2) to reflect the maximum and
212 minimum values of sound energy during the evaluation period (L_{Cpeak} , L_{AFmax} and L_{AFmin}).
213 Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to statistically analyse the relationships
214 between subjective variables (noise effects) and objective acoustic variables (percentiles

215 of various sound indicators). This parametric statistical approach was applied following
216 verification of assumptions for normality (Shapiro test), homoscedasticity (Breusch-
217 Pagan test), linearity (RESET test), and independence (Durbin-Watson test). The
218 statistical power achieved given the sample size (105 participants) was 0.94, exceeding
219 the recommended minimum power of 0.8 suggested by prior studies (Fritz and
220 MacKinnon, 2007; Cohen, 1988).

221
222
223

3. Results and discussion

224 *3.1. Standard acoustic variables related to the statistical time structure of sound*

225 This subsection examines the relationships between standard objective acoustic variables
226 and subjective variables related to urban noise effects perceived by pedestrians. Table 3
227 shows the correlation coefficient between subjective and acoustic variables, along with
228 their corresponding levels of significance. It is immediately apparent that all percentiles,
229 except L_{AF1} for effect (c), demonstrate statistically significant correlations with all studied
230 noise effects. But let us first analyse for which percentiles the highest values of the
231 correlation coefficient are obtained in relation to the noise effects studied. The L_{AF50}
232 indicator, representing average street noise levels, is notably the only percentile
233 significantly correlated at $p \leq 0.001$ with all subjective variables. This indicator explains
234 approximately 50 % of the variance in subjective responses such as irritability (a), startle
235 (b), elevation of the volume of nearby conversations (e) and telephone conversations (g)
236 and annoyance (i). Moreover, it yields Pearson correlation coefficients equal to or higher
237 than those of other percentiles for 6 of the 9 analysed effects: (a) irritability ($r = 0.71$), (d)
238 interrupting conversation ($r = 0.66$); (e) raising volume ($r = 0.70$), (f) interrupting phone
239 ($r = 0.60$), (g) raising phone ($r = 0.69$) and (h) perceived street noise ($r < 0.66$). In contrast,
240 two effects —startle (b) and annoyance ears (c)— show strongest correlations with

241 percentiles related to background and minimum noise levels (L_{AF90} , L_{AF95} , L_{AF99}). A
242 percentile related to background noise, L_{AF90} , is the best percentile ($r = 0.71$) for (b) startle
243 effect, and two percentiles related with minimum noise levels, L_{AF95} and L_{AF99} , are the
244 best for (c) auditory annoyance ($r = 0.67$). For (b) startle, the value of the correlation
245 coefficient achieved for L_{AF50} is very close to them ($r = 0.69$), but for (c) auditory
246 annoyance, the value for L_{AF50} is some distance ($r = 0.59$). The L_{AF5} percentile, associated
247 with the highest noise levels, achieves the highest Pearson correlation coefficient for (i)
248 annoyance ($r = 0.78$) and only this effect shows the highest correlation coefficient values
249 for the group of peak and mean percentiles levels (L_{AF1} , L_{AF5} , L_{AF10} and L_{AF50}). In this
250 case, the L_{AF50} indicator also reaches a relatively close value ($r = 0.73$). Two main
251 conclusions emerge from these results. Firstly, the optimal percentile varies depending
252 on the specific noise effect studied, ranging from peak noise percentiles to those
253 associated with background or average noise levels. Secondly, if one percentile must be
254 selected to consistently evaluate all studied effects, L_{AF50} clearly emerges as the most
255 robust choice and, moreover, its capacity to explain the appearance and intensity of the
256 effects, in general, never far from that achieved at the most appropriate percentile for this
257 purpose.

258 Next, focusing on the noise effects, Table 3 reveals that irritability (a) and perceived street
259 noise (h) show statistically significant correlations ($p \leq 0.001$) across all analysed
260 percentiles. The highest correlation coefficient was observed for (i) annoyance ($r = 0.78$).
261 Conversely, interruption phone (f) had the lowest maximum correlation coefficient ($r =$
262 0.60 , for L_{A50} percentile) among all effects. This effect also reaches the lowest
263 significant value of all those in the table, $r = 0.40$ ($p < 0.05$), for the L_{AF1} percentile. A
264 particularly notable finding from Table 3 is that the L_{AF50} percentile indicator consistently
265 shows the strongest linear correlations with all effects related to spoken communication

266 disturbances (d-g) and perceived noisiness of the street (h). This result suggests that
 267 perceptions of street noisiness may be closely linked to its impacts on communication
 268 quality within urban settings.

269

270 Table 3. Correlation coefficient between subjective variables and acoustic variables
 271 related to the time structure of the sound wave.

	L_{AF1}	L_{AF5}	L_{AF10}	L_{AF50}	L_{AF90}	L_{AF95}	L_{AF99}
a)	0.62 ^{***}	0.69 ^{***}	0.71 ^{***}	0.71 ^{***}	0.64 ^{***}	0.62 ^{***}	0.59 ^{***}
b)	0.50 ^{**}	0.62 ^{***}	0.66 ^{***}	0.69 ^{***}	0.71 ^{***}	0.70 ^{***}	0.68 ^{***}
c)	0.34 ^{n.s.}	0.45 [*]	0.49 ^{**}	0.59 ^{***}	0.66 ^{***}	0.67 ^{***}	0.67 ^{***}
d)	0.52 ^{**}	0.61 ^{***}	0.62 ^{***}	0.66 ^{***}	0.61 ^{***}	0.60 ^{***}	0.57 ^{**}
e)	0.55 ^{**}	0.62 ^{***}	0.65 ^{***}	0.70 ^{***}	0.64 ^{***}	0.62 ^{***}	0.58 ^{**}
f)	0.40 [*]	0.51 ^{**}	0.54 ^{**}	0.60 ^{***}	0.57 ^{**}	0.56 ^{**}	0.54 ^{**}
g)	0.52 ^{**}	0.60 ^{***}	0.63 ^{***}	0.69 ^{***}	0.62 ^{***}	0.60 ^{***}	0.56 ^{**}
h)	0.59 ^{***}	0.63 ^{***}	0.64 ^{***}	0.66 ^{***}	0.64 ^{***}	0.62 ^{***}	0.60 ^{***}
i)	0.77 ^{***}	0.78 ^{***}	0.76 ^{***}	0.73 ^{***}	0.59 ^{***}	0.55 ^{**}	0.49 ^{**}

272 n.s. Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$).

273 * Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

274 ** Significant at $p \leq 0.01$.

275 *** Significant at $p \leq 0.001$.

276

277 The results described above suggest that the occurrence and intensity of the analysed
 278 noise effects may be closely related to the statistical temporal structure of urban noise
 279 environments, possibly indicating causal relationships among certain noise effects.

280 To analyse these possibilities in greater detail, the Pearson correlation coefficients
 281 obtained for each percentile were plotted against each of the subjective variables (a-i) in
 282 Figure 2. In this figure, correlation coefficients (r) for each noise effect are represented
 283 as a series of seven points, ordered from left to right corresponding to percentiles L_{AF99} ,
 284 L_{AF95} , L_{AF90} , L_{AF50} , L_{AF10} , L_{AF5} , and L_{AF1} . Figure 2 clearly indicates groups of noise effects

285 sharing similar correlation patterns (e.g., effects d, e, f, g, and h), distinctly differing from
 286 the patterns of other effects (e.g., effects a, b, c, and i). This observation suggests the
 287 value of examining whether statistically significant relationships exist between these
 288 correlation patterns across different subjective effects. Such relationships could help
 289 elucidate the reasons behind the similarities or differences in the intensity of noise effects
 290 and establish possible connections either among different noise effects or between these
 291 effects and the temporal features of urban noise environments. To achieve this, a linear
 292 correlation analysis was conducted between the patterns of correlation coefficient values
 293 across different pairs of noise effects. Table 4 show the resulting correlation coefficients.
 294 The independent variable is represented by the effects listed in the rows of Table 4. For
 295 example, the correlation coefficient pattern for (a) irritability significantly predicts the
 296 pattern for (d) interrupting a conversation with someone nearby, yielding a Pearson
 297 correlation coefficient of 0.76 ($p \leq 0.05$).
 298

299
 300 Figure 2. Correlation coefficients between the percentiles L_{AF99} (leftmost point), L_{AF95} ,
 301 L_{AF90} , L_{AF50} , L_{AF10} , L_{AF5} and L_{AF1} (rightmost point), for each of the noise effects (a-i).

302

303 Table 4 illustrates that effect (a), irritability, shares similar correlation patterns with
304 effects (d), (e), (g), and (h), all significant at $p \leq 0.05$. These findings suggest that, in a
305 statistically significant way, with a moderate intensity: (I) irritability is linked to
306 disruptions in communication quality caused by noisy environments, or (II) the perceived
307 noisiness of a street is associated with irritability induced by urban noise.

308 The strongest correlations among these percentile structures in explaining noise effects
309 occur between effects (d), (e), (f), (g), and (h). Table 4 clearly shows significant
310 correlations between every possible pair of these five effects. In some cases, the Pearson
311 correlation coefficients reach values of 0.98 or higher, indicating that more than 96% of
312 the variance in percentile correlation patterns is shared among these effects. This strongly
313 suggests that these five effects may originate from similar temporal structures of urban
314 noise. Therefore, the perception of street noisiness may be closely linked to the disruptive
315 impacts of noise on spoken communication quality.

316

317 Table 4. Correlation coefficients between the values structure of the correlation
318 coefficients of variables a)-i) in Fig. 2.

	b)	c)	d)	e)	f)	g)	h)	i)
a)	n.s.	n.s.	0.76*	0.77*	n.s.	0.77*	0.79*	n.s.
b)		0.91**	n.s.	n.s.	0.97***	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
c)			n.s.	n.s.	0.82*	n.s.	n.s.	-0.86*
d)				0.98***	0.84*	0.99***	0.98***	n.s.
e)					0.80*	1.00***	0.99***	n.s.
f)						0.81*	0.78*	n.s.
g)							0.99***	n.s.
h)								n.s.

319 n.s. Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$).

320 * Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

321 ** Significant at $p \leq 0.01$.

322 *** Significant at $p \leq 0.001$.

323

324 Notably, the correlation between the percentile structure for (b) startle and those for (c)
325 annoyance ears ($p < 0.01$), and especially (f) interrupting phone ($p < 0.001$), suggests that
326 these effects may be triggered by similar temporal characteristics of the urban noise
327 environment. This may indicate that the temporal patterns of noise causing startle also
328 contribute to ear discomfort or interfere with phone conversations. This finding is
329 consistent with the statistically significant relationship reported in Table 4 between ear
330 annoyance and phone call interruption ($p < 0.05$).

331 Remarkably, the correlation structure for the annoyance effect (i) shows no significant
332 similarity with those of the other effects, except for a single negative correlation with (c)
333 annoyance ears ($p < 0.05$). Two key conclusions can be drawn from this finding. First, it
334 suggests a substantial difference between the objective temporal features of the sound
335 environment responsible for the annoyance effect and those underlying the other eight
336 effects. Second, it may indicate that opposing temporal structures of the sound
337 environment underlie two distinct responses: the more physiological ear annoyance and
338 the more psychological perception of general annoyance from ambient noise.

339

340 *3.2. Non-standard acoustic variables related to the statistical time structure of sound*

341 This section introduces a novel approach to analysing the relationships between perceived
342 noise effects and sound indicators related to the statistical temporal variability of sound
343 levels. In urban noise studies, percentiles calculated from instantaneous A- and F-
344 weighted sound pressure levels are typically used to characterize statistical temporal
345 variability. The new method proposed calculates standard percentiles ($L_1, L_5, L_{10}, L_{50}, L_{90},$
346 L_{95}, L_{99}) based on second-by-second recordings of several conventional acoustic
347 indicators: $L_{Zeq}, L_{Ceq}, L_{Aeq}, L_{A1eq}$, Loudness, Loudness Level, L_{Cpeak}, L_{AFmax} , and L_{AFmin} . To
348 assess the relevance of statistical temporal variability in noise effect prediction, Pearson

349 correlation coefficients for these percentiles were compared with those obtained from the
350 indicators themselves (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2024a) and with standard A- and F-
351 weighted percentiles (see Section 3.1).

352

353 For this analysis, the percentile with the highest regression performance was selected
354 (optimal percentile). Additionally, based on previous results from Section 3.1, the L_{50}
355 percentile was used as a reference, since it is the one with which the best results are
356 generally achieved. Figure 3 presents correlation coefficients between various noise
357 effects (a-i) and the traditional indicators, including comparisons with the L_{50} percentile
358 and the optimal percentile. Table 5 summarizes explicitly which percentile is optimal for
359 each effect-indicator pair.

360 A detailed examination of the results presented in Figure 3 reveals several significant
361 findings:

- 362 - For the majority of the 81 studied effect-indicator pairs, at least one percentile
363 outperforms the traditional acoustic indicator. Only five pairs show no
364 improvement, and even then, differences are minimal (under 3%). These
365 exceptions involve the "noisy street" (effect h) with L_{Zeq} and L_{Ceq} , and
366 "annoyance" (effect i) with L_{Aeq} , L_{A1eq} , and Loudness Level. These results
367 emphasize the importance of considering the temporal variability of sound in
368 urban noise assessment.
- 369 - Another noteworthy result concerns indicators associated with extreme sound
370 levels (L_{Cpeak} , L_{AFmax} , L_{AFmin}) which showed notably stronger correlations when
371 analysed through percentiles, compared to using the indicators directly, even for
372 those effects where the base indicators do not show significant relationships.

373 - The L_{50} percentile generally surpasses the base indicator and performed close to
374 optimal across indicators and effects, particularly for high-level indicators (L_{Cpeak}
375 and L_{AFmax}) and for A-weighted or level-dependent weighted indicators. Although
376 for specific noise effects, like "annoyance" (effect i) or "annoyance ears" (effect
377 c), it performed slightly below the best percentile. These results support the use
378 of L_{50} as a reliable, generalized reference percentile. Studying other sound aspects,
379 similar results to those obtained in the present work on L_{50} primacy have been
380 published by several authors (Can and Gauvreau, 2015; Nilsson et al., 2007).
381 Other authors (Chang et al., 2024) find that L_{10} (not L_{50}) may be a better indicator
382 to explain how noisy is perceived the waiting areas in a Chinese children's
383 hospital. In this case, it is not possible to assert the existence of discrepancies with
384 respect to the findings reported in this study, since Chang et al. (2024) does not
385 analyse L_{50} and in our work, for the LAF indicator, the L_{10} percentile is better
386 than the L_{90} percentile, as occurs in the work of Chang et al. (2024).

387 - Additionally, for all effects, except those related to telephone communication (f
388 and g), the best correlations are generally found with the percentiles associated to
389 Z- or C-weighted indicators. This observation could be particularly significant
390 given the widespread use of A-weighted indicators in urban noise assessments.
391 This finding and the well-known limitation of telephone systems in reproducing
392 low-frequency sounds effectively (Jiang et al., 2022), show a coherence of the
393 results and reinforce their quality. Note that even for annoyance (i), which is the
394 only effect for which a clear improvement in the value of r was found in those
395 indicators not weighted Z or C when using traditional energy based indicators
396 (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2024a), when it is now analysed on the basis of the
397 percentiles of all the indicators, the highest correlation of annoyance with the Z

398 or C weighted indicator percentiles is achieved using L_{Cpeak} ($r = 0.80$), similar to
399 the best previous value obtained with L_{Aleq} ($r = 0.81$) (Barrigón Morillas et al.,
400 2024a).

401

402

403

Figure 3. Correlation coefficients between the noise effects (a-i) with respect to the noise indicators (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2024a) and their percentiles L_{50} and L_{XX} (percentile with the higher value of r coefficient).

404 - Finally, it can be seen in Figure 3 that there are two groups of behaviours. A first
 405 group for the Z- or C-weighted indicators, and a second group for the rest of the
 406 indicators. In each of these two groups, it can be said that the way in which the
 407 indicator is weighted is more important than the indicator used, whether it is
 408 obtained by means of an energy average or by means of a maximum or minimum
 409 energy value. This finding may indicate that the ability of statistical time
 410 indicators to explain the effects of noise is conditioned to a greater extent by the
 411 weighting used than by whether the indicator is derived from an energy average
 412 or is an indicator of maximum or minimum values.

413 Table 5. Number indicating the best percentile for each effect (a-i)/indicator pair.

Effect	L_{AFx}	L_{AFMax}	L_{AFMin}	L_{Cpeak}	L_{A1eq}	L_{Aeq}	L_{Ceq}	<i>Loudness</i>	<i>LoudLevel</i>	L_{Zeq}
a)	10	10	50	50	10	50	50	5	50	50
b)	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	50	90
c)	95	95	95	95	95	95	95	95	95	95
d)	50	50	50	5	50	50	5	50	50	5
e)	50	50	50	10	50	50	5	50	50	5
f)	50	50	50	10	50	50	5	90	50	5
g)	50	50	50	10	50	50	5	50	50	5
h)	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	5
i)	5	1	1	5	1	5	5	1	1	5

414

415 Now, an analyse of results showed in table 5 reveals that:

416 - The noise effect being analysed is more influential than the indicator itself in
 417 determining the most relevant percentile. For example, “startle” (effect c) is best
 418 explained by L_{95} across all indicators; “annoyance ears” (effect b) by L_{90} (except
 419 for Loudness Level, where L_{50} is better). In contrast, no single indicator
 420 consistently determines the best percentile. The most stable combination is
 421 *Loudness Level* with the L_{50} percentile.

422 - For indicators not Z- or C-weighting, the best percentile for predicting the impact
423 of noise on spoken communication in urban settings (effects d to g) is L_{50} . This
424 pattern is also observed when assessing perceived street noisiness also including
425 C-weighted indicators. Thus, across nine indicators, the results suggest a strong
426 link between the perceived noisiness of a street and the interference that noise
427 causes in verbal communication.

428 Table 5 and Fig. 3 also supports the conclusions drawn from Figure 2 and Table 2. This
429 is particularly significant as earlier conclusions (from Section 3.1) were based on a single
430 sound indicator whereas the current findings are supported by percentiles across nine
431 indicators. It can be observed that:

432 - For all indicators, the effects (b) startle and (c) annoyance ears are best explained
433 by percentiles associated with background noise levels. Several studies have
434 examined various aspects related to the startle effect, either in animals (Ison, J.R.,
435 1979; Hoffman, H.S., et al., 1964; Flaten M.A. et al., 2005) or in humans (May,
436 D.N., 1971). The experimental conditions of these studies (laboratory settings that
437 do not include percentile-based acoustic indicators and that do not consider a
438 single general acoustic environment, but rather distinguish between a target noise
439 and a separate background noise) differ significantly from those adopted in the
440 present study. It is considered that there is complementarity between the results
441 shown in this work and those obtained in the cited bibliography, and it is believed
442 that, given the complex nature of psychoacoustic mechanisms and the different
443 factors that may be associated with noise perception, new research, with
444 multidisciplinary teams of specialists in acoustic engineering, neuropsychology
445 and otorhinolaryngology, are necessary to understand the relationship between
446 physical noise characteristics and noise effects occurrence.

- 447 - A notable difference is observed between the temporal characteristics associated
448 with effect (i) annoyance and those associated with the other effects with the
449 largest difference with effect (c) annoyance ears.
- 450 - Depending on the specific noise effect, the optimal percentile varies, and this
451 variation is consistently observed across all nine indicators.
- 452 - The 50th percentile appears most frequently and the Pearson correlation values
453 for L_{50} are generally close to those of the best percentile —with the largest
454 differences seen in effects (c) annoyance ears and (i) annoyance. These findings
455 (now with ten different indicators) allow to conclude that if one percentile must
456 be chosen to evaluate all effects, L_{50} is the most reliable.

457 As demonstrated by the results of this study, the use of indicators that define the temporal
458 statistical structure of sound environments generally improves the ability of sound
459 indicators to explain the effects of urban noise on pedestrians. Among them, the L_{50}
460 indicator shows, on average, better performance than the rest of the percentiles. In
461 addition, in other studies, researchers have shown that L_{50} aligns more closely with
462 subjective assessments of sound quality and pleasantness, especially in urban contexts
463 (Can & Gauvreau, 2015; Can et al., 2016; Ricciardi et al., 2015). Its potential to better
464 reflect the typical auditory experience, suggests that L_{50} could be a useful indicator for
465 spatial characterisation and perceptual evaluation of acoustics environments, overcoming
466 to L_{Aeq} . Other authors have also shown that L_{50} may serve as a reliable indicator for the
467 continuous assessment of noise, due to its reduced sensitivity to anomalous events, an
468 aspect of particular importance given the growing relevance of dynamic noise mapping.
469 Therefore, the use of L_{50} in noise policy possibly can contribute to a more targeted and
470 effective noise management strategies.

471 All these results may indicate that, in addition to the energetic aspects normally
472 considered when relating noise effects to received doses, the statistical temporal structure
473 of noise may also play a critical role in the occurrence of such effects. Consequently, this
474 structure may be significant for predicting the effects that urban noise environments may
475 have on people.

476 Considering these findings, may be of interest that urban planners and policy makers
477 review current noise assessment protocols and mitigation strategies by incorporating
478 statistical temporal structures of acoustic indicators, such as temporal percentiles, into
479 both the diagnosis and monitoring phases. By integrating these acoustic descriptors into
480 urban noise models and action plans, decision-makers can more effectively target
481 interventions to enhance acoustic comfort and public well-being in diverse urban
482 environments. Finally, public communication strategies can be enhanced using
483 percentile-based noise maps that reflect actual perceptual impacts rather than solely
484 energetic averages, promoting more transparent and targeted decision-making.

485

486 **4. Conclusions**

487 This study demonstrates the significant role of the statistical temporal structure of urban
488 noise in explaining and predicting its effects on pedestrians. The following conclusions
489 are supported by the results obtained with both the percentiles of the traditional L_{AF} sound
490 indicator and the percentiles of nine other indicators that are not traditionally used with
491 percentiles. The optimal percentile for describing the impact of noise varies depending
492 on the specific effect examined. Nevertheless, the L_{50} percentile consistently proved to be
493 the most robust overall indicator, displaying strong correlations across all subjective
494 variables and supporting the use of L_{50} as a reliable, generalized reference percentile. In
495 particular, it effectively captured the influence of noise on communication-related effects,

496 such as the interruption of conversations and the need to raise one's voice, as well as the
497 general perception of a street being noisy. These findings suggest a close relationship
498 between perceived street noisiness and the degradation of spoken communication quality
499 due to urban noise exposure.

500 The results further indicate that there is a large difference between the objective
501 characteristics of the sound environment that cause the annoyance effect and those that
502 cause the other eight effects analysed. In fact, the discomfort in the ears, likely more
503 physiological, and the feeling of ambient annoyance, possibly more psychological, seem
504 to be caused by reversed temporal noise structures. These distinctions highlight the
505 complexity of human responses to urban noise and emphasize the limitations of
506 traditional energy-based indicators. In this regard, the dynamic variation of sound levels
507 over time emerges as a key explanatory factor for the manifestation and intensity of noise
508 effects.

509 Complementary analysis using non-standard acoustic indicators supports and extends
510 these conclusions. Percentiles derived from second-by-second recordings of nine
511 conventional indicators (spanning average energy, peak levels, and minimum levels)
512 yielded improved predictive capacity compared to the indicators themselves. This was
513 particularly evident for high-level indicators such as L_{Cpeak} and L_{AFmax} , whose percentiles
514 showed markedly stronger correlations with all studied effects, even when the original
515 indicators were not significantly related. A similar trend, although more moderate, was
516 observed for the minimum-level indicator L_{AFmin} .

517 The outcomes found in the present study underscore that the effect under analysis, rather
518 than the acoustic indicator used, primarily determines the most relevant temporal
519 percentile. Moreover, the type of frequency weighting applied was found to be more
520 influential than whether the indicator represents average or extreme energy values.

521 Indicators using Z or C frequency weighting (preserving low-frequency spectral content)
522 proved to be more effective for predicting urban noise effects when temporal statistical
523 features were employed, regardless of whether they reflect mean, maximum, or minimum
524 levels. This finding may be particularly relevant given the widespread use of A-weighted
525 indicators in urban noise evaluations, suggesting that it may be worth reconsidering, or at
526 least re-examining, the extent to which these metrics should remain the standard in such
527 assessments.

528 In closing, and as a general summary of the outputs found in the present study, it can be
529 said that, although the average sound energy during exposure remains important for
530 explaining certain noise effects, as traditionally assumed in dose–response models, this
531 work reveals that the temporal evolution of sound levels throughout the exposure period
532 plays a critical role for all analysed effects. Accordingly, the statistical temporal structure
533 of urban noise should be recognized as a fundamental dimension in the assessment and
534 prediction of noise-induced impacts on urban populations.

535

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543

544 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

545 J.M.B.M.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis,
546 Investigation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing—Original Draft, Writing—Review and
547 Editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

548 D.M.G.: Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation,
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553 Writing—Review and Editing, Visualization.

554 All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

555

556 **Declaration of competing interest**

557 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
558 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

559

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563

564 **Data availability**

565 Data will be made available upon reasonable request.

566

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